

INTEGRATING GRAMMAR AND COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS IN TEACHING ENGLISH CLASSROOMS

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Abstract. *In this article the most important integrated skills are explained through a Communicative way and Methods of teaching foreign language in EFL classrooms. Learning four skills aids for utilizing authentic materials and challenges make them interact naturally in English language. Finally, the integrated-skill approach can be highly motivating to students of all ages and backgrounds.*

Key words: *Integrated skills, methods and communicative skill, approaches and communication.*

ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ГРАММАТИКИ И КОММУНИКАТИВНЫХ НАВЫКОВ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА В КЛАССАХ

Аннотация. *В этой статье наиболее важные интегрированные навыки объясняются через коммуникативный способ и методы обучения иностранному языку в классах EFL. Изучение четырех навыков помогает использовать аутентичные материалы и задачи, которые позволяют им естественно взаимодействовать на английском языке.*

Наконец, подход интегрированных навыков может быть очень мотивирующим для студентов всех возрастов и слоев общества.

Ключевые слова: *Интегрированные навыки, методы и коммуникативные навыки, подходы и коммуникация.*

Introduction: Teaching work is mental and physical at the same time. It requires dedication, behavior, persuasion, communication and gathering attention of learners. In short description, it is complex process that why it conveys everything which is related to teaching. language is even harder because it conveys different ways or approaches that involve hard work.

For teaching foreign language instructors should engage the language effectively and use it spontaneously that's why language teachers absorb everything that is related to their language and proficiency. They should pay attention to the communication, role plays, authentic materials and variety of activities. Also, teachers should give feedbacks to their students in two ways such as, peer and group feedback. Teaching a foreign language in EFL classroom requires lots of methods, cultural awareness real life contexts, grammar integrated tasks, virtual discussions, reflective journals and adaptability to learners. By making an engaging effective environment helps a lot them for absorbing language.

While learning process integrating skills are vital which are reading, writing, speaking and listening. Using these skills efficiently in the EFL classrooms learners can enhance their knowledge base easily. This integrating skills aids pre-school learners, high students to utilize the language naturally with the help of mimics and natural words. The teacher of the course can choose the most appropriate skill relying on the students' enthusiasm. Some learners found the interaction

more important rather than writing or reading. From the demand of the students, teachers have chance to conduct their lesson with the most important skill. Integration skills refers to the interaction of the four skills all together during the instruction. Why is it important? Integrating all these skills are the true opening way of real meaningful communication between speakers.

However, even if it is possible to get knowledge very well without one or two skills it can't give full guarantee to achieve the high success in another language in the term of adequate knowledge.

In previous years most of the teachers used only grammar rules for teaching. A great example is that if people rely on grammar translation method it may not help to engage it sufficiently. In that case it will be time-consuming and require a long preparation. So this way causes boredom during the classroom. For making the lesson enjoyable methods are the good way to the instructors. In teaching process methods are grammar translation method, audio lingual method, direct method and communicative method.

The grammar translation method is the oldest method and the vast majority of the teachers used in the past while their lessons. This method mainly focuses on grammar and vocabulary. If the students are in this type of learning it will be tedious because they can only rely on set of grammar rules. The next step of the method is the translation of texts. Students are exposed to authentic texts in the foreign language and then translate these texts into their mother tongue. Translation helps to develop the ability to understand and interpret texts, in addition to contributing to the acquisition of vocabulary. It will be clear example in the sentence.

-The boy..... a car slowly every day. (is driving, drives)

-Pupils.... already.... the project. (has finished, have done)

The direct method is characterized oral communication. It happens during oral production.

Teacher – centred method. In summary, the direct method is an effective approach to foreign language teaching that emphasizes oral communication and immersion in authentic and meaningful situations. Although it has some limitations, the direct method may be particularly suitable for students with more advanced levels of proficiency. However, the direct method also has some limitations. For example, it can be difficult to assess student learning objectively and systematically. Additionally, the direct method may be more challenging for students with lower proficiency levels, who may have difficulty following instructions in a language they have not yet mastered

The audio-lingual method is particularly used for intensive way like diplomacy, military and other purposes. One of the main advantage of the audio lingual method it is daily practice of communication in language which can lead to dramatic improvement in their fluency and accuracy.

Apart from these, learners who have high desire for travelling abroad it will be practical way to them in order to listen daily conversation and dialogue through audio lingual method. It emphasized repetition, memorization, and intensive practice of the target language, using oral and listening exercises to develop communicative skills

Communicative method is using the real language in the EFL classrooms with pupils, students or learners. The important objective of the method to increase the learners' communicative skills. In this section the role of the teacher is observer like the coach hears the speakers' sentences and give feedbacks in order to make their speech better and correct their

mistakes one-by-one. It provides the opportunity to interact in the target language in an authentic way, helping them to develop their communication skills and feel freedom in their speech.

For example:

- describe the embarrassing moment in your life (2 minutes speech)
- making dialogues between two people (giving questions that's related to every day life and listen their conversation carefully)

In this part they should create a short story and describe it step-by-step. When the speaker is making a speech the teacher can check good and bad sides or find mistakes, also give suggestions about their speaking section. Nowadays, communicative approach has been used by the learners because it has been widespread around the world. It provides students with an opportunity to communicate in the target language in a meaningful and authentic way, helping them to develop their communication skills and feel more confident when speaking to people from different backgrounds.

For teachers communicative skills are important too. The reasons is that makes the information meaningful. During the interaction it will be verbal and non-verbal

In verbal communication tone, body language and set of vocabulary words, eye contact clarity, adaptibility are vital.

Tone it is crucial making the voice lower or louder.

Body language using gestures, mimics

Eye contact looking at learners directly

Adaptation to adapt to the environment

In non-verbal communication using visual aids, observing reactions, nodding and facial expressions and self-reflections.

Visual aids like posters or presentation for making the lesson interesting

Nodding for clarification

Observing- following speakers or students.

In summary for teaching foreign language in EFL classrooms teachers should be unique in both fields like language, communication and adaptation too. Those strategies that are given above can lead to organize lessons in EFL classrooms effectively and accurately. In that catching or absorbing the language will be easier compared other ways.

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